

THE CREATION OF CONDITIONS SUITABLE FOR A SMALL AGE AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE USE OF MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: This article highlights the fact that the theoretical and methodological foundations of the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in primary classes are improved on the basis of the possibilities of logic, speed, creativity, the acceptable form, means and methods of using innovative pedagogical technologies in primary classes are improved on the basis of communicative and analytical skills, psychological impact skills, content formation model.

Keywords: innovation, theoretical-methodological foundations, psychological impact, form, medium, communicative, creativity, model, analytical skills, technology

The process of development of innovative activities begins precisely at the level of personal causality. At the level of specialization, we are faced with much more complex organizers of personality creative opportunities and the orientation towards an innovative attitude to the unit of reflexivity implies the imposition of constant problems and their solution in different ways.

The main focus is on knowledge rather than innovative activity technology. The main goal is to involve students in the innovative process in which, together with the marketer, they test their author's program to identify the methods of innovating and assess the effect of the achievement.

At the same time, the entire pedagogical team acts together in the context of creative cooperation. The method of scientific investigation and the interleaving of Group proceedings make up the guruhli investigations and form the basis of the technology for organizing students in this experimental space.

Based on the principle of self-development of the innovative process, innovation not from above, but from below, an innovative idea is initiated by a certain group of teachers and begins to work.

With the support of other colleagues for the implementation of an innovative idea, they also begin to hold a job in this way. In these cases, a group of teachers also carry out pilot work with a passion for working in a new way. On this basis, the school will cause the beginning of work to introduce a novelty into the educational process. Of course, even in this case, there may be contradictions in the implementation of the novelty. In this case, the majority opinion wins.

The application of innovation to the learning process on the basis of the above initiative “from above” cannot be contrasted with the initiative “from below”. But when the novelty is introduced centrally from above, it is observed that the innovative initiative of teachers is at a lower level.

For this reason, school teachers should develop a logical sequence in planning the introduction of innovations into pedagogical activity: the goals and objectives of the novelty, the real possibilities of its inclusion in the educational process, the creation of a creative environment for the pedagogical community, the model of working educational work in a new way, the logical sequence of the school in In the future, the school should work in the developer mode, making sure that quality guarantees efficiency. The pedagogical team, on the other hand, must make sure that the creative teacher-the creative pedagogical team-becomes a complex.

Today, mihim plays an important role in the education of primary class `pupils not only in innovative pedagogical technology methods and tools, but also in improving the content and quality of the educational process, the use of Information Technology in the educational process. In particular, in the introduction of information technology to education in developed countries, the integration of their technical means is the main direction.

In this regard, even the concept of “Multimedia” appeared, which indicates the complex use of most technical means in teaching. The most important thing with

the use of multimedia will be to teach students to select the necessary information. The task of the teacher will consist in topping the information and helping.

The teacher is also a guide in the field of knowledge. Also, the introduction of information technology into the educational process has caused a change in the role of a teacher, with pedagogy becoming more of an educational researcher, organizer, consultant and programmer. In the following years, positive changes have occurred and are giving in the process of equipping with information technology, the content of the educational system, the forms of its organization and improving quality.

It is known that in the traditional teaching method of teachers, a lot of time is devoted to conducting practical work. This is a very important component of expert training. It provides support not only to strengthen the theoretical knowledge of the student, to increase the effectiveness of mastering the educational material, but also to generate practical skills in a particular Soha. At the moment when technologies are developing at a rapid pace, it is required to improve the standards for practical training in each academic year. To do this, it is necessary to make additional expenses.

Taking into account the above, we can say that a new system specialist helps to solve important tasks for training personnel, there is a need to introduce a new effective, inclusive pedagogical style. To do this, it is necessary to achieve that classes in training workshops will be not only interesting for all students, but also comfortable easy.

It is necessary to achieve that classes will be easy for all students, not only intense, but also comfortable. It is necessary that the classes are able to attract, take into account all mental and didactic factors; demonstrate the processes in a lively way, increase the effectiveness of training and mastering the taught science as a whole, ensure the possibility of self - assessment in the subject of acquired knowledge.

It is from this point of view that the implementation of modern information technology contributes to the optimal solution of the above tasks and the elimination of a number of disadvantages of the traditional method of training.

A Virtual stand is an educational practical stand or training qualification workshop that helps students consolidate theoretical knowledge, acquire the necessary skills through computer software and technology.

As a result of their introduction, an even higher quality of the educational process for training specialists is ensured when comparing traditional education. This is achieved due to the use of specialized educational methodological manuals, which include questions for automatized teacher (educator) and testing systems, test assignments and self-examination, a quick update of the methodological basis of the educational process. We will have the opportunity to study organizational forms of teaching, modern information technologies and various educational institutions. This ensures that, to some extent, the value of the diplomas of different institutions is equal.

Thus, innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process lead to:
the educational process will help its students more individually, taking into account the exact level of training, abilities, mastering new material, pace, interests and inclinations;

readers' knowledge activities can be enhanced;

support and development of their self-improvement, educational and professional interests and aspirations;

strengthening interdisciplinary ties in educational processes complex study of the phenomena of being continuous and dynamic updating of the educational process at the expense of flexibility, factoriness, forms of organization and their improvement;

the use of problematic computer tools of teaching in all educational institutions, as well as virtual stands;

improving the technological base of the educational process with modern technical means.

Therefore, in modern technologies, the pedagogical process should be carried out on the basis of personality-oriented technologies of teaching.

Therefore, the level of development of successive generations was almost indistinguishable. Under these conditions, Ya.A.Komensky gave birth to an authoritarian technology of teaching, a traditional "class-lesson" system.

The personality-oriented technologies of training will be characteristic of the following basic principles:

humanity, that is, to show respect and love to a person in every possible way, to help him, to look at his creative abilities with confidence, to give up rape to the fullest;

cooperation, that is, pedagogy and students democratism, equality, partnership;

free upbringing, that is, giving the person freedom and independence of choice in a wide and narrow framework of his life activity, bringing results from internal sensations, not from external influences, the communicative basis of personality-oriented technologies is a human-personal approach to the student in the pedagogical process.

A new look at the person will consist of:

in the pedagogical process, an individual is not an object, but a subject-each student is the owner of the ability, and most are the owner of the talent;

high ethical values (generosity love, hard work conscience, etc.) are the main qualities of an individual.

Democratization of relations includes:

equalization of reader and pedagogue rights;

the right of the reader to choose freely ;

right to error;

right to have one's own point of view;

Attitude of educators and students: not to ban, not to control, not to manage together, not to force, to persuade, not to order, to organize, not to change, to allow free selection.

The main content of the new relationship is vos keeh from the pedagogy of violence, which does not give an effective result in the current conditions and is considered non-human. The problem is not in the absolutism of this principle, but in the identification of its rational criteria.

Free training is defined by:

- trust-based free suitability;
- stimulating interest in educational material, knowledge and active serious thinking;
- reliance on student independence and initiative;
- ensuring the implementation of requirements by indirect methods through the team.

The essence of the new individual approach is that in the educational system it is necessary to move from the student to the academic subject, and not from the student to the student, taking into account the existing capabilities of the students, to develop, improve and enrich them.

A modern new interpretation of an Individual approach consists of:

- abstinence from targeting the average student;
 - search for new personality traits;
 - compilation of individual programs of Personality Development;
- In a personal approach, the following will be necessary in the first place:
- to see a unique person in the image of each student, to respect, understand, accept, believe in him. To have in the educator the belief that all students are willing;
 - to bring to the person an announcer a proverb, a supporter, a benefactor, the creation of situations, that is, reading satisfaction and joy;
 - not allowing direct coercion, not emphasizing backwardness and other shortcomings, not touching the elegance of flour;
 - in the pedagogical process, to provide and assist students with the opportunity to realize their abilities.

Innovation is a series of important and systematic innovations that arise on the basis of various initiatives and updates, and are considered promising for the evolutionary discovery of education, and also have a positive effect on the development of the educational environment.

Pedagogical innovation is a theoretical tool of education and upbringing by introducing changes in pedagogical activity that were previously unknown in the educational process.

The general logic of the various methods and means of organizing the knowledge and activities of students, teaching in cooperation serves to implement the principles. These complexes in turn form the technological basis of collaborative teaching. Only the didactic system seen on such a basis and the method tested in the pedagogical process, the means can serve as technology. The basis of the didactic system is a complex of teaching methods, which are based on a certain theoretical basis, the concept of education on principles.

Innovative educational technology is a modern advanced technology of education in institutions. The purpose of this technology is to strengthen the interest of teachers in their science by using innovative methods in improving the effectiveness of the lesson in the educational process, to educate their creative approach to the study of subjects, to teach independent work with literature, to solve the tasks of indicating the use of the link between disciplines. On the basis of this method, which bears the name of modern educational technologies, a number of problems are finding their solution.

New computer information technologies such as Motion Pictures, teleconferencing, transliteration, e-book are serving to activate the learning process. Innovative educational technologies are relevant not only in science, but also in the study of techniques. In the study of techniques, it is recommended to use this educational technology in the following order: the imposition of a technical task by the educator so that the material on the topic is mastered by the teachers, the ways of solving the technical task are carried out by them. In this, teachers write down

problematic questions and their own scientific assumptions and draw up an interactive communication plan.

Modern educational technologies motivate teachers towards scientific and creative activities and independent thinking. It educates the skills of being able to connect the knowledge gained in them with practice and to be able to use various resources in acquiring new knowledge. Teaches to compact the knowledge base. The main thing is the reason for the formation of creative communication between the master and the disciple.

The effectiveness of innovative processes in the educational system, as well as the use of innovative methods in improving the effectiveness of the elementary class lesson due to the imposed Nozom requirements, depend on the conditions for the development and introduction of innovations, the purposeful continuous application of traditional methods of Education. There are cases of abandonment of traditional methods that are effective in some cases.

It is felt, as if putting innovation against teaching, which has been tested in the experiment and is giving a positive result. That is why it is desirable that positive experiences in the traditional educational system harmonize with innovations. Nowadays, the interest, attention to the application of innovative educational technologies in the educational system is gaining momentum day by day. An innovative approach ensures that training in the educational process is interesting and effective. At present, information communication tools are widely used in their knowledge acquisition. Especially working at a computer, looking for and mastering the necessary information from different networks is becoming their interesting pastime. This is also an innovative approach, which assumes the content of special knowledge, skills and qualifications.

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